

SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF MODERN FORMS OF ORGANIZING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK

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Abstract. *Systematic work on the implementation of the process of self-education in higher education, teaching students to work independently, creatively and socially active, able to independently find their place in socio-political life, new staff with the ability to set and solve future tasks is the basis for the formation of the next generation. There fore, in this article we will try to reveal the pedagogical problems of modern forms used in the organization of self-education of students and ways to solve them.*

Key words: *self-education, credit module, independent thinking, organization, creativity.*

СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ФОРМ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. *Систематическая работа по реализации процесса самообразования в высшей школе, обучению студентов работать самостоятельно, творчески и социально активными, умеющими самостоятельно находить свое место в общественно-политической жизни, новыми кадрами, способными ставить и решать. задачи будущего – это основа формирования следующего поколения. Поэтому в данной статье мы попытаемся раскрыть педагогические проблемы современных форм, используемых в организации самообразования учащихся, и пути их решения.*

Ключевые слова: *самообразование, кредитный модуль, самостоятельное мышление, организованность, креативность.*

Introduction: Today's reforms in the educational system are aimed at developing students' independent thinking, eliminating problems related to the formation of creative thinking and practical skills in students based on individual educational trajectories. A step-by-step transition to the implementation of these tasks is planned in higher education institutions. Today, the main problems in the higher education system are the lack of independent study hours, the lack of independent learning, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, and entrepreneurial skills in students, the lack of organizational skills in the educational process, the introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies, and not meeting the needs of the times. . Therefore, increasing the share of independent study hours in the higher education system, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process , orienting the educational process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard one of the main tasks of today is the widespread introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials into the educational process based on international educational standards. In modern conditions, according to all the possibilities of the educational process, it is required to develop and socialize the

individual and direct the abilities of independent, critical and creative thinking. It is necessary to train highly qualified specialists according to the requirements of consumers, to form the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in their chosen specialties, to independently acquire knowledge and to train them in practical activities. [1]

Main part; Due to the fact that independent education is interpreted as a problem for the development of organizational skills of students, the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" approved on September 23, 2020 states that "Independent education is carried out individually and the professional, intellectual, spiritual and cultural development of students" serves" can be cited in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the higher education system": Wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials based on educational standards, active involvement of highly qualified teachers and scientists from foreign partner educational institutions in educational-pedagogical activities, training master classes, training courses" enough.[3]

Results and Discussions; Currently, further improvement of the educational process, curricula and programs of higher education on the basis of the wide introduction of new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, qualitative renewal of the master's scientific education process and the introduction of modern organizational forms are among the main problems, and based on these problems, the curriculum and The main goal is to create a new generation of widely introduced new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, qualitatively update the master's scientific-educational process, and introduce modern organizational forms. In the conditions of today's globalization, it is desirable to use advanced pedagogical technologies and active methods in the educational process, to apply newly produced technical tools, to encourage more students to work independently, and to widely use various ways of teaching lessons from best practices. [4] Another important point is that it is necessary to ensure the effective organization of training of special subjects in order to develop the inclination, abilities, knowledge and skills of students studying in the higher education system, to develop them as specialists in their chosen fields. As in any society, the main problem in the development of our republic is the training of qualified specialists who can withstand competition in the conditions of the market economy. In recent years, large-scale work has been done and is being done on the training of specialist personnel, improving its quality and efficiency. In particular, special attention is being paid to developing qualities such as independence, creativity, entrepreneurship, and activity of trained specialists. [5] How to do independent work in educational institutions is done by each student. In order to achieve success, the student must work on himself with patience and without fear of difficulties. This is planned and implemented by the student himself. Problems and changes in all aspects of society affect the process of training students in higher education institutions and set new requirements. Currently, there is a great need for specialists and personnel who have theoretical knowledge and practical skills, are adaptable to changes, think freely, and can independently solve their professional and life problems. At the same time, higher education institutions require their students to be well-rounded, independent thinkers, and have organizational skills. The fulfillment of such requirements is ensured by teaching them to acquire knowledge throughout their life. In the conditions of active education, acquired knowledge,

acquired skills and competences are formed in a systematic and logically complete manner and allow to be used in various production situations. Activating learners allows them to develop their independent learning skills. As a solution to the problem of developing organizational skills of students in the process of independent education, we can say that the educational process in higher education institutions is gradually transferred to the credit module system. In the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, it was indicated that by 2030, 85 percent of all higher education institutions (HEIs) in the republic, including 33 higher education institutions in the 2020/2021 academic year, will be transferred to the credit module system. The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an evaluation model based on a collection of module technologies of teaching and a credit measure. [6] Its implementation as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the principle of credit module, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating. Therefore, the credit-module system consists not only of teaching lessons based on innovative educational technologies, but also of teaching the student to learn independently, to have a new attitude to education, to acquire the necessary and deep theoretical knowledge, and to form practical skills based on the demand of the labor market. In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturity of the student. It can be said that it is aimed at ensuring the education of a person of knowledge throughout his life and at forming human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements . The introduction of the credit-module system is an important factor in the cooperation between the teacher and the student. In modular education, the pedagogue organizes, manages, advises and checks the student's learning process. And the student moves independently towards the directed object. The greatest emphasis is placed on independent learning of students. Development of organizational skills of students in the process of independent education of higher education institutions is one of the main issues. [7] In this regard, we believe that it is appropriate to carry out systematic work in the following directions. Firstly, on the basis of reforms in the educational system implemented today, in order to increase the awareness and activity of learners, it is necessary to organize the teaching process in such a way that students consciously and actively acquire scientific knowledge and the methods of their practical application, they have creative initiative and independence in their educational activities, thinking, speaking. focus on ensuring that it serves the development of technology. Secondly, popularizing the works of innovative teachers who have achieved success in this field, establishing and developing work on exchange of experience. Thirdly, in today's era of digital economy, to establish ways of forming and formalizing information on independent education of students based on the requirements of the time. Fourth, to create opportunities to use foreign experience in developing organizational skills of students in the process of independent education. [8]

Conclusion (Conclusion); Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that it is necessary to establish systematic work in the implementation of the independent education process in higher education institutions, to teach students to work independently, to be creative and socially active, to find their place independently in social and political life, to set promising tasks and to solve problems. will be the basis for forming a new generation of personnel with the ability to do. High-quality communication between the teacher and the student in the process of independent

work, the role and importance of the teacher in the process of independent work of students, management functions, modern forms of independent work of students using information and communication technologies, mobile technologies - as a pedagogical problem.

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